

UNIVERSITÉ PARIS-SACLAY

Faculté des Sciences, Orsay

Laboratoire de Physique des 2 Infinis Irène Joliot-Curie

**Analytical Calculations on the
Dielectric Wave-guide Design of
TWAC**

Maleesh Dissanayake Mudiyansele

Supervisor: Dr. Guillaume Martinet

Submitted: February 10, 2023

Abstract

Due to the huge cost of implementation, and the environmental impact of conventional particle accelerators, the reduction of their footprint has been recently the focus of discussion. With the TWAC project, a new accelerator technology has been introduced that is not only lightweight and compact in size, but also capable of producing an energy gain gradient of over 100 MeV/m. In this study, the analytical calculations were carried out on the dielectric wave-guide design of the TWAC project in Python. The numerical solutions were obtained for selected geometries, and cutoff frequencies for different modes were calculated and compared with the previously obtained results in [1]. The dielectric thickness of the waveguide was also investigated for different configurations.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	The TWAC Project	1
1.2	Different accelerating structures	2
1.2.1	Radio-Frequency (RF) cavity acceleration	2
1.2.2	THz-driven acceleration	2
1.2.3	LASER plasma wakefield acceleration	3
1.3	Theory	3
1.3.1	EM waves and Maxwell's equations	3
1.3.2	Propagation of an EM wave and different accelerating modes	5
2	Circular waveguide partially filled with dielectric medium	7
2.1	General solutions for a circular waveguide in vacuum [2]	7
2.1.1	TE Modes	8
2.1.2	TM Modes	9
2.2	General solutions for a circular waveguide partially filled with dielectric medium [3]	10
2.2.1	Longitudinal electric field and magnetic field components in different domains	11
2.2.2	Tangential electric field and magnetic field components in different domains	11
2.2.3	The system of equations obtained at $\rho = a$	11
3	Results and Discussion	13
3.1	Numerical solution of Equation 44	13
3.2	Diagram of $k_{c_2}a$ as a function of $k_{c_1}a$	14
3.3	Cutoff frequencies for different modes	15
3.4	Dielectric thickness for different configurations	17

4	Conclusions	20
5	Literature Cited	22
6	Acknowledgement	23
7	Python scripts used in this study	24
7.1	Solving the general equation	24
7.2	Diagram of $k_{c_2}a$ as a function of $k_{c_1}a$ for the first 4 modes for 1 GHz . . .	28
7.3	Diagram of $k_{c_2}a$ as a function of $k_{c_1}a$ for different frequencies	30
7.4	Cutoff frequency	36
7.5	Dielectric thickness	39

List of Figures

1	This figure shows the dispersion characteristic of a wave guide. The cutoff frequency of the wave guide and the phase velocity and the group velocity are too displayed. Image source: [4]	6
2	This figure shows the geometry of a circular waveguide. Image source: [2] .	7
3	This figure shows a schematic of a circular waveguide partially filled with a dielectric material. Image credit: [3].	10
4	This figure represents the two sides of Equation 47. The blue curve corresponds to the right part of the equation, and the yellow curve to the left part. The colored points correspond to the intersections between these two curves. These points correspond to the solutions of the equation, and they represent the different modes of the accelerator.	14
5	This figure shows the diagram of $k_{c_2}a$ vs $k_{c_1}a$ for the first 4 modes, at a frequency of 1.0 GHz. Blue, Red, Green and Yellow represent the first four modes in order.	15
6	This figure shows the diagram of $k_{c_2}a$ vs $k_{c_1}a$ for the first 4 modes for 400 different frequencies ranging from 0 to 18.6 GHz. Blue, Red, Green, and Yellow represent the first four modes in order.	16
7	This figure shows the behavior of $k_{c_2}a$ against $k_{c_1}a$ with purely imaginary and real $k_{c_1}a$ plotted in the left and right halfplanes respectively. Image source: [1]	17

List of Tables

1	This table compares the expected values and the calculated values for the normalized cutoff wavelength.	17
2	This table shows the dielectric thickness for different values of inner radius, where $\epsilon_r = 3.75$, and $v_\phi = 0.998c$, first directly calculated values and then the observed values using CST.	18
3	This table shows the dielectric thickness for different dielectric materials, where $a = 1.5mm$, and $v_\phi = 0.998c$	18

1 Introduction

1.1 The TWAC Project

Particle accelerators play a significant role in the modern-day world since they have a variety of real-world applications, other than the well-known obvious ones in nuclear physics, material science, high-energy physics, and particle physics. They have a lot of applications in the field of medicine (for example, proton therapy is a type of radiation therapy that uses protons to treat cancer), and also in industry (i.e sterilization of medical equipment, food irradiation, crosslinking of plastics, etc).

Since usually particle accelerators come with a huge cost and a considerable amount of environmental impact, there is a timely need to reduce the footprint of the particle accelerators (comparably). In the TWAC project, a novel way is proposed with a new structure sustaining the accelerating wave pushing up the particle energy. Here, an idea for an accelerator is proposed that is both lightweight and small in size. By breaking through current technological barriers, industrial accelerators will be developed which can produce energy gain gradients of over 100 MeV/m. Not only that, but this accelerator will also provide significantly enough time for medical studies to be conducted.

The main objective is to achieve stronger accelerating fields by utilizing higher frequencies and dielectric materials that can reduce the occurrence of the breakdown so that a high-gradient accelerating structure can be obtained. In general, the ultrashort electron bunches are accelerated by a guided THz field in a dielectric material. Typically, conventional radio frequency (RF) cavities can only produce accelerating fields up to 100 MV/m. The proposed design aims to surpass this limit by utilizing a cylindrical waveguide filled with dielectric material chosen appropriately.

1.2 Different accelerating structures

1.2.1 Radio-Frequency (RF) cavity acceleration

In particle accelerators, RF (radio frequency) structures are used to make an electromagnetic field that helps to speed up the charged particles. These structures usually have many cavities made of materials like copper that are lined up along the path the particles move along. These cavities are powered by RF generators that make electromagnetic fields that vibrate at specific frequencies. Usually they are in the GHz region. As the charged particles move through the cavities, they get energy from the electromagnetic field. The process is repeated for a few times, so by the time they reach the end of the accelerator, they have a lot of energy.

In normal RF accelerators, the usual way of making particles go faster is by using a field that is a few tens of MV/m strong (Mega-Volt per meter). Some of these accelerators, like the ones used in synchrotron radiation sources, can even make the field up to 50 MV/m strong. But there are other types of RF accelerators that can make the field even stronger, like superconducting RF accelerators and normal conducting RF accelerators, which can make fields up to 100 MV/m or more.

1.2.2 THz-driven acceleration

THz-driven accelerators are a type of particle accelerator that uses very strong electromagnetic fields in the THz (terahertz) range of frequencies to make charged particles go faster. The THz range is between microwaves and infrared, and it covers frequencies around 0.1 to 10 THz.

In THz-driven accelerators, the charged particles are usually made to go faster by a strong, short pulse of THz, which is created by an intense laser pulse shining on a special material called a photoconductive antenna. The laser pulse makes a lot of electron-hole pairs in the photoconductive antenna, which then creates a large electric current that makes the THz pulse. Since the THz frequencies are much higher than the ones used in normal RF accelerators, they have the ability of making particles go even faster. This could lead

to making small, high-energy accelerators for different uses like medicine, industry, and scientific research.

1.2.3 LASER plasma wakefield acceleration

Laser-plasma accelerators, also called laser-wakefield accelerators, are a type of particle accelerator that uses powerful laser pulses to create a wave in a gas, called a plasma wave. This wave is then used to speed up charged particles, like electrons or protons, to very high energies in a short distance.

A powerful laser pulse is aimed at a gas, which causes it to turn into a plasma. This pulse creates a wave in the plasma called a wakefield, which can be used to speed up the charged particles. The laser pulse itself doesn't touch the particles, but creates a wave that the particles can ride, like surfing a wave.

The main advantage of laser-plasma accelerators is their ability to achieve very high accelerating gradients (fields of hundreds of GV/m) over short distances (typically a few millimeters). This could lead to making small, high-energy accelerators for different uses like medicine, industry, and scientific research.

1.3 Theory

1.3.1 EM waves and Maxwell's equations

The electromagnetic fields should satisfy the laws of physics and the boundary conditions in a given geometry for a structure. The behavior of electric and magnetic fields and their interactions with charges and currents is explained by the Maxwell's equations. The related equations for a vacuum are given as the following.

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{B} = \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} + \mu_0 \vec{J} \quad (4)$$

For any given medium these equations can be further extended as follows.

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{D} = \rho \quad (5)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (7)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{H} = \frac{\partial \vec{D}}{\partial t} + \vec{J} \quad (8)$$

The electric field and the magnetic field can be obtained by directly integrating the Maxwell's equations. Alternatively, one can use the Helmholtz equation by utilizing the electric vector potential and the magnetic vector potential as follows.

$$\vec{\nabla}^2 \vec{\Pi}_e + \beta^2 \vec{\Pi}_e = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\vec{\nabla}^2 \vec{\Pi}_m + \beta^2 \vec{\Pi}_m = 0 \quad (10)$$

The electric field and the magnetic field can be derived by solving the introduced equations in the following way.

$$\vec{H}_e = -\vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{\Pi}_e \quad (11)$$

$$\vec{E}_e = \frac{-1}{j\omega\epsilon} \left(\vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{\Pi}_e \right) \quad (12)$$

$$\vec{E}_m = -\vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{\Pi}_m \quad (13)$$

$$\vec{H}_m = \frac{1}{j\omega\mu} \left(\vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{\nabla} \wedge \vec{\Pi}_m \right) \quad (14)$$

These equations will be used to solve the problem of the circular waveguide partially

filled by a dielectric medium.

1.3.2 Propagation of an EM wave and different accelerating modes

An EM wave propagating along the Z direction should satisfy Equation 15, where k_z is the propagation constant along the Z direction.

$$E(z) = E(0) \exp(\pm k_z z) \quad (15)$$

The propagation constant can be described as shown in Equation 16. Here k is the wave number of the incident wave and k_c is the cutoff wave number of the medium.

$$k_z = \sqrt{k^2 - k_c^2} = \frac{1}{c} \sqrt{\omega^2 - \omega_c^2} = \frac{2\pi}{c} \sqrt{f^2 - f_c^2} \quad (16)$$

The phase velocity (v_p) and the group velocity (v_g) are defined in Equation 17, and Equation 18. They can also be presented in a scatter diagram as shown in Figure 1.

$$v_p = \frac{\omega}{\beta} \quad (17)$$

$$v_g = \left(\frac{d\beta}{d\omega} \right)^{-1} \quad (18)$$

In a given RF structure, the EM waves tend to propagate as a mode that depends on the geometry of the structure. There are mainly four types of propagation with respect to the orientation of the fields compared to the direction of the propagation of the wave.

1. **TE Mode:** This is known as the Transverse Electric mode, which means that the field has only a magnetic component (H) along the direction of propagation, and the electric component is in the plane transverse to the propagation direction.
2. **TM Mode:** This is known as the Transverse Magnetic mode, and the field has only an electric component (E) along the direction of propagation, and the magnetic component is in the plane transverse to the propagation direction.

Figure 1: This figure shows the dispersion characteristic of a wave guide. The cutoff frequency of the wave guide and the phase velocity and the group velocity are too displayed. Image source: [4]

3. **TEM Mode:** In this case, both E and B fields have only components transverse to the direction of propagation.
4. **HEM Mode:** This is known as the Hybrid Electromagnetic Mode. The hybrid mode is considered when the edge conditions are such that they cannot be satisfied by a purely TM or TE mode. In this case, the E and B fields can have a component transverse and/or parallel to the direction of propagation.

2 Circular waveguide partially filled with dielectric medium

The special case of a circular waveguide partially filled with the dielectric medium can be realized as a further extension of the problem of a circular waveguide in a vacuum. Therefore, first, let's realize the general solutions for the basic situation.

2.1 General solutions for a circular waveguide in vacuum [2]

A circular waveguide is a waveguide with a circular cross-section and it is used for the propagation of electromagnetic waves in different frequency ranges. The purpose of a waveguide is to guide electromagnetic waves from one point to another without any significant loss of energy. The waveguide's dimensions are chosen so that the operating frequency is below the cutoff frequency, ensuring that only the lowest-order mode can propagate. The geometry of such a waveguide is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: This figure shows the geometry of a circular waveguide. Image source: [2]

The cylindrical components of the transverse fields can be derived from the longitudinal components as follows.

$$E_\rho = \frac{-j}{k_c^2} \left(\beta \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} + \frac{\omega \mu}{\rho} \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \phi} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$E_\phi = \frac{-j}{k_c^2} \left(\frac{\beta}{\rho} \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \phi} - \omega \mu \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \right) \quad (20)$$

$$H_\rho = \frac{j}{k_c^2} \left(\frac{\omega \epsilon}{\rho} \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \phi} - \beta \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \rho} \right) \quad (21)$$

$$H_\phi = \frac{-j}{k_c^2} \left(\omega \epsilon \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \rho} + \frac{\beta}{\rho} \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \phi} \right) \quad (22)$$

where $k_c^2 = k^2 - \beta^2$, and the propagation constant is assumed as $e^{-j\beta z}$. For $e^{+j\beta z}$ propagation, we can replace β with $-\beta$ in all expressions.

2.1.1 TE Modes

For TE modes, $E_z = 0$, and H_z becomes a solution to the wave equation as below.

$$\nabla^2 H_z + k^2 H_z = 0 \quad (23)$$

Assuming $H_z(\rho, \phi, z) = h_z(\rho, \phi)e^{-j\beta z}$ and $h_z(\rho, \phi)$ as,

$$h_z(\rho, \phi) = (A \sin n\phi + B \cos n\phi)J_n(k_c\rho) \quad (24)$$

the transverse field components are obtained as shown in the below equations.

$$E_\rho = \frac{-j\omega\mu n}{k_c^2\rho} (A \cos n\phi - B \sin n\phi)J_n(k_c\rho) e^{-j\beta z} \quad (25)$$

$$E_\phi = \frac{j\omega\mu}{k_c} (A \sin n\phi + B \cos n\phi)J'_n(k_c\rho) e^{-j\beta z} \quad (26)$$

$$H_\rho = \frac{-j\beta}{k_c} (A \sin n\phi + B \cos n\phi)J'_n(k_c\rho) e^{-j\beta z} \quad (27)$$

$$H_\phi = \frac{-j\beta n}{k_c^2\rho} (A \cos n\phi - B \sin n\phi)J_n(k_c\rho) e^{-j\beta z} \quad (28)$$

The cutoff wave number k_c

Considering the boundary condition that $E_{tan} = 0$ on the waveguide wall, we can write

$E_\phi = 0$ at $\rho = a$.

This leads to the propagation constant as given in Equation 29, with a cutoff frequency given in Equation 30.

$$\beta_{nm} = \sqrt{k^2 - k_c^2} = \sqrt{k^2 - \left(\frac{p'_{nm}}{a}\right)^2} \quad (29)$$

$$f_{c_{nm}} = \frac{k_c}{2\pi\sqrt{\mu\epsilon}} = \frac{p'_{nm}}{2\pi a\sqrt{\mu\epsilon}} \quad (30)$$

2.1.2 TM Modes

For TM modes, $H_z = 0$, and assuming $E_z(\rho, \phi, z) = e_z(\rho, \phi)e^{-j\beta z}$, we take $e_z(\rho, \phi)$ as,

$$e_z(\rho, \phi) = (A \sin n\phi + B \cos n\phi)J_n(k_c\rho) \quad (31)$$

Then the transverse field components are obtained as shown in the below equations.

$$E_\rho = \frac{-j\beta}{k_c}(A \sin n\phi + B \cos n\phi)J'_n(k_c\rho) e^{-j\beta z} \quad (32)$$

$$E_\phi = \frac{-j\beta n}{k_c^2\rho}(A \cos n\phi - B \sin n\phi)J_n(k_c\rho) e^{-j\beta z} \quad (33)$$

$$H_\rho = \frac{j\omega\epsilon n}{k_c^2\rho}(A \cos n\phi - B \sin n\phi)J_n(k_c\rho) e^{-j\beta z} \quad (34)$$

$$H_\phi = \frac{-j\omega\epsilon}{k_c}(A \sin n\phi + B \cos n\phi)J'_n(k_c\rho) e^{-j\beta z} \quad (35)$$

The cutoff wave number k_c

In this case, the boundary condition can be applied directly such that $E_z(\rho, \phi, z) = 0$ at $\rho = a$.

This leads to the propagation constant as given in Equation 36, with a cutoff frequency given in Equation 37.

$$\beta_{nm} = \sqrt{k^2 - k_c^2} = \sqrt{k^2 - \left(\frac{p_{nm}}{a}\right)^2} \quad (36)$$

$$f_{c_{nm}} = \frac{k_c}{2\pi\sqrt{\mu\epsilon}} = \frac{p_{nm}}{2\pi a\sqrt{\mu\epsilon}} \quad (37)$$

2.2 General solutions for a circular waveguide partially filled with dielectric medium [3]

The previous case can be further extended with the introduction of a dielectric material that helps to increase the breakdown threshold which limits the maximum accelerating field within a simple waveguide. A waveguide with a circular cross-section of inner radius a and outer radius b is considered in this situation and a schematic can be realized as Figure 3.

Figure 3: This figure shows a schematic of a circular waveguide partially filled with a dielectric material. Image credit: [3].

Even though the objective of solving this problem is to obtain the dispersion relation of the waveguide, there is no simple analytical solution for this problem. Instead, we can solve the problem numerically for a given geometry (for fixed a and b), and then solve the equations to obtain $k(\omega)$, for a given frequency, as suggested in [1].

By solving the Helmholtz equations (considering the boundary conditions), the electric vector potential and the magnetic vector potential are obtained as shown in Equation 38 and Equation 39 respectively.

$$\bar{\Lambda}^{(e)} = \begin{cases} A_{mn} J_m(K_{c_1} \rho) \cos(m\phi) e^{-jh_{mn}z}; & 0 \leq \rho \leq a \\ A'_{mn} R_m(k_{c_2} \rho) \cos(m\phi) e^{-jh_{mn}z}; & a \leq \rho \leq b \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

$$\bar{\Lambda}^{(m)} = \begin{cases} B_{mn} J_m(K_{c_1} \rho) \sin(m\phi) e^{-jh_{mn}z}; & 0 \leq \rho \leq a \\ B'_{mn} S_m(k_{c_2} \rho) \sin(m\phi) e^{-jh_{mn}z}; & a \leq \rho \leq b \end{cases} \quad (39)$$

2.2.1 Longitudinal electric field and magnetic field components in different domains

Longitudinal electric field and magnetic field components in the vacuum and in the dielectric media can be derived as given in Equation 40 and Equation 41 respectively.

$$E_z = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{j\omega\varepsilon_0} (k_0^2 - h_{mn}^2) \bar{\Lambda}^{(e)} = -\frac{1}{j\omega\varepsilon_0} k_{c1}^2 \bar{\Lambda}^{(e)}; & 0 \leq \rho \leq a \\ -\frac{1}{j\omega\varepsilon_0\varepsilon_r} (\varepsilon_r k_0^2 - h_{mn}^2) \bar{\Lambda}^{(e)} = -\frac{1}{j\omega\varepsilon_0\varepsilon_r} k_{c2}^2 \bar{\Lambda}^{(e)}; & a \leq \rho \leq b \end{cases} \quad (40)$$

$$H_z = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{j\omega\mu_0} (k_0^2 - h_{mn}^2) \bar{\Lambda}^{(m)} = -\frac{1}{j\omega\mu_0} k_{c1}^2 \bar{\Lambda}^{(m)}; & 0 \leq \rho \leq a \\ -\frac{1}{j\omega\mu_0} (k_0^2 - h_{mn}^2) \bar{\Lambda}^{(m)} = -\frac{1}{j\omega\mu_0} k_{c2}^2 \bar{\Lambda}^{(m)}; & a \leq \rho \leq b \end{cases} \quad (41)$$

2.2.2 Tangential electric field and magnetic field components in different domains

Tangential electric field and magnetic field components in the vacuum and in the dielectric media can be derived as given in Equation 42 and Equation 43 respectively. Note that, in each field component, the first part corresponds to the solution in $0 \leq \rho \leq a$ and the second part to $a \leq \rho \leq b$.

$$E_\theta = \frac{-1}{j\omega\varepsilon} \left[\frac{1}{\rho} jh_{mn}m \begin{pmatrix} A_{mn}J_m(k_{c1}\rho) \\ A'_{mn}R_m(k_{c2}\rho) \end{pmatrix} \cos(m\theta)e^{-jh_{mn}z} - j\omega\varepsilon \begin{pmatrix} k_{c1}B_{mn}J'_m(k_{c1}\rho) \\ k_{c2}B'_{mn}S'_m(k_{c2}\rho) \end{pmatrix} \sin(m\theta)e^{-jh_{mn}z} \right] \quad (42)$$

$$H_\theta = \frac{1}{j\omega\mu} \left[\frac{-1}{\rho} jh_{mn}m \begin{pmatrix} B_{mn}J_m(k_{c1}\rho) \\ B'_{mn}S_m(k_{c2}\rho) \end{pmatrix} \cos(m\theta)e^{-jh_{mn}z} + j\omega\mu \begin{pmatrix} k_{c1}A_{mn}J'_m(k_{c1}\rho) \\ k_{c2}A'_{mn}S'_m(k_{c2}\rho) \end{pmatrix} \sin(m\theta)e^{-jh_{mn}z} \right] \quad (43)$$

2.2.3 The system of equations obtained at $\rho = a$

Then we consider the continuity of the longitudinal and tangential components of the electric and magnetic fields at $\rho = a$, and obtain the following relationship given by Equation 44.

$$\left(\frac{1}{x} \frac{J'_m(x)}{J_m(x)} - \frac{\epsilon_r R'_m(y)}{y R_m(y)}\right) \left(\frac{1}{x} \frac{J'_m(x)}{J_m(x)} - \frac{\epsilon_r S'_m(y)}{y S_m(y)}\right) = m^2 \left(\frac{1}{x^2} - \frac{\epsilon_r}{y^2}\right) \left(\frac{1}{x^2} - \frac{1}{y^2}\right) \quad (44)$$

where,

$$x = k_{c_1} a, \quad k_{c_1} \text{ is the cutoff wave number of vacuum.}$$

$$y = k_{c_2} a, \quad k_{c_2} \text{ is the cutoff wave number of the dielectric medium.}$$

$$k_0^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2}, \quad k_0 \text{ is the wave number of the incident wave.}$$

$$y^2 - x^2 = (\epsilon_r - 1) k_0^2 a^2, \quad \epsilon_r \text{ is the dielectric constant of the material.}$$

$$y^2 - \epsilon_r x^2 = (\epsilon_r - 1) h_{mn}^2 a^2, \quad h_{mn} \text{ is the propagation constant along the z-direction.}$$

J_m is the Bessel function of the first kind of order m .

J'_m is the derivative of the Bessel function of the first kind of order m .

N_m is the Bessel function of second kind of order m (also called the Neumann function).

N'_m is the derivative of the Bessel function of second kind of order m .

$$R_m(k_{c_2} \rho) = N_m(k_{c_2} b) J_m(k_{c_2} \rho) - J_m(k_{c_2} b) N_m(k_{c_2} \rho)$$

$$N_m = Y_m$$

$$R_m(k_{c_2} a) = R_m(y) = Y_m(k_{c_2} b) J_m(k_{c_2} a) - J_m(k_{c_2} b) Y_m(k_{c_2} a)$$

$$R_m(y) = Y_m\left(y \frac{b}{a}\right) J_m(y) - J_m\left(y \frac{b}{a}\right) Y_m(y)$$

$$R'_m = \frac{dR_m}{d(k_{c_2} \rho)}$$

$$S_m(y) = Y'_m\left(y \frac{b}{a}\right) J_m(y) - J_m\left(y \frac{b}{a}\right) Y'_m(y)$$

$$S'_m = \frac{dS_m}{d(k_{c_2} \rho)}$$

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Numerical solution of Equation 44

Using the relations, $k_{c_1} = \sqrt{k_0^2 - h_{mn}^2}$, and $k_{c_2} = \sqrt{\epsilon_r k_0^2 - h_{mn}^2}$, Equation 45 is derived.

$$k_{c_2}^2 = k_{c_1}^2 + (\epsilon_r - 1)k_0^2 \quad (45)$$

Taking $x = k_{c_1}a$, $y = k_{c_2}a$, and multiplying the equation by a^2 , we obtain Equation 46.

$$y = \sqrt{x^2 + (\epsilon_r - 1)k_0^2 a^2} \quad (46)$$

Then we substitute this relationship to Equation 44 and obtain Equation 47.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{J'_m(x)}{xJ_m(x)} - \epsilon_r \frac{R'_m(\sqrt{x^2 + (\epsilon_r - 1)k_0^2 a^2})}{\sqrt{x^2 + (\epsilon_r - 1)k_0^2 a^2} R_m(\sqrt{x^2 + (\epsilon_r - 1)k_0^2 a^2})} \right) \left(\frac{J'_m(x)}{xJ_m(x)} - \frac{S'_m(\sqrt{x^2 + (\epsilon_r - 1)k_0^2 a^2})}{yS_m(\sqrt{x^2 + (\epsilon_r - 1)k_0^2 a^2})} \right) \\ & = m^2 \left(\frac{1}{x^2} - \frac{\epsilon_r}{x^2 + (\epsilon_r - 1)k_0^2 a^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{x^2} - \frac{1}{x^2 + (\epsilon_r - 1)k_0^2 a^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

We can plot the two parts of this equation as a function of x, for the case of $m = 1$, $\epsilon_r = 6.1$, $c = 3.10^8$, $a = 0.03568$, $b = 0.05567$ and $f = 1.0$ GHz. This yields Figure 4.

From the intersecting points we obtain the x values ($x = k_{c_1}a$), and then using Equation 46, the related y values ($y = k_{c_2}a$) are derived. The first intersecting point corresponds to the first solution, and therefore to the first mode of the accelerator, and the second point corresponds to the second solution and therefore to the second mode. This repeats for the other roots as well.

Each intersecting point represents a hybrid mode defined as HEM_{mn} , where m is the order of the Bessel function (taken as 1 here), and n corresponds to the n^{th} solution. Therefore, Figure 4 corresponds to the modes HEM_{1n} . At the cutoff frequency, the modes are necessarily TE or TM.

Our examination revealed four separate roots for the fundamental equation, each corresponding to a distinct mode of acceleration. A fifth root was identified when we reduced

Figure 4: This figure represents the two sides of Equation 47. The blue curve corresponds to the right part of the equation, and the yellow curve to the left part. The colored points correspond to the intersections between these two curves. These points correspond to the solutions of the equation, and they represent the different modes of the accelerator.

the x-axis step size, however, our focus was solely on the initial four modes (i.e. the first four roots).

For the incident wave with a frequency of 1.0 GHz, the behavior of the quantities $x = k_{c_1} a$ and $y = k_{c_2} a$, can be plotted as shown in Figure 5.

3.2 Diagram of $k_{c_2} a$ as a function of $k_{c_1} a$

The process is repeated for several frequencies in order to obtain a succession of points in the diagram. In Figure 6, 400 different frequencies have been utilized, ranging from 0 to 18.6 GHz. When raising the frequency, we observed that a branch of a mode in the diagram moves upwards or in other words it gets shifted towards the left.

Figure 5: This figure shows the diagram of $k_{c_2}a$ vs $k_{c_1}a$ for the first 4 modes, at a frequency of 1.0 GHz. Blue, Red, Green and Yellow represent the first four modes in order.

Figure 7 shows the set of solutions of the fundamental equation (Equation 47) for the case of $m=1$ as explained in [1]. This was the theoretically expected set of curves.

Comparing Figure 6 with Figure 7, it is clear that they exhibit similar behavior for the real $k_{c_1}a$, which directly confirmed our computation algorithms. In this study, only the real values of $k_{c_1}a$ were considered. The same analysis could be extended to purely imaginary $k_{c_1}a$ values as well.

3.3 Cutoff frequencies for different modes

At the cutoff frequency, the propagation constant should be equal to 0; i.e $h_{mn} = 0$. The relations, $k_{c_1} = \sqrt{k_0^2 - h_{mn}^2}$, and $k_{c_2} = \sqrt{\epsilon_r k_0^2 - h_{mn}^2}$, reduce into $k_{c_1} = k_0$, and $k_{c_2} = \sqrt{\epsilon_r} k_0$ respectively. This leads to $x = k_0 a$ and $y = \sqrt{\epsilon_r} x$.

Substituting these relations into Equation 44, the RHS becomes zero, and yields Equation 48, with $y = \sqrt{\epsilon_r} x$.

$$\left(\frac{1}{x} \frac{J'_m(x)}{J_m(x)} - \frac{\epsilon_r R'_m(y)}{y R_m(y)} \right) \left(\frac{1}{x} \frac{J'_m(x)}{J_m(x)} - \frac{\epsilon_r S'_m(y)}{y S_m(y)} \right) = 0 \quad (48)$$

The x values which satisfy the equation are determined and the cutoff wavenumbers k_0

Figure 6: This figure shows the diagram of $k_{c_2}a$ vs $k_{c_1}a$ for the first 4 modes for 400 different frequencies ranging from 0 to 18.6 GHz. Blue, Red, Green, and Yellow represent the first four modes in order.

are calculated as $k_0 = \frac{\omega}{c}$. Then the cutoff frequency for a given x value can be derived as shown in Equation 49.

$$f_c = \frac{xc}{2\pi a} \quad (49)$$

Then we calculate the cutoff frequencies of different accelerating modes for a special case where the dielectric constant is 6.1 and the ratio between the outer and inner radii is 0.667. These determined values are then compared (as shown in Table 1) with the values obtained in [1].

With respect to Table 1, it is clear that the obtained results for normalized cutoff wavelength are highly accurate (in this case, for two decimal places).

Figure 7: This figure shows the behavior of $k_{c2}a$ against $k_{c1}a$ with purely imaginary and real $k_{c1}a$ plotted in the left and right halfplanes respectively. Image source: [1]

Accelerating mode	Expected Value from [1]	Calculated Value
HEM_{11}	2.3643	2.3630
HEM_{12}	1.3994	1.3985
HEM_{13}	0.9705	0.9704
HEM_{21}	1.8130	1.8120
HEM_{22}	1.1832	1.1826
HEM_{31}	1.5136	1.5129
HEM_{32}	1.0290	1.0285
HEM_{41}	1.2937	1.2932

Table 1: This table compares the expected values and the calculated values for the normalized cutoff wavelength.

3.4 Dielectric thickness for different configurations

Considering the waveguide, the main limit to accelerating a field to higher values is the electric breakdown. In general, a higher electrical breakdown threshold allows the waveguide to facilitate a higher accelerating field. The threshold breakdown and the dielectric constant are unique to a given dielectric material. Therefore, choosing the appropriate

dielectric material is important in designing the waveguide.

Inner radius (a)	Calculated dielectric thickness (μm)	Dielectric thickness using CST(μm)
1 mm	157	169.5
1.5 mm	124	130
2 mm	102	104

Table 2: This table shows the dielectric thickness for different values of inner radius, where $\epsilon_r = 3.75$, and $v_\phi = 0.998c$, first directly calculated values and then the observed values using CST.

In this section, for a fixed value of the inner radius (a), and for a given dielectric material ($\epsilon_r = 3.75$), we determined the dielectric thickness of the material to have the phase velocity of the beam be approximately equal to the speed of light ($v_\phi = 0.998c$) at a working frequency of 165 GHz. The calculated values are then compared with the determined values using CST software in Table 2.

Looking at the two types of results for the dielectric thickness, it is clear that both types (direct computation and CST software method) provide reasonable accuracy in computing the thickness of the dielectric material. Also, the thickness of the dielectric decreases when the inner radius is increased. Additionally, the difference between the two types of results reduces when we increase the inner radius.

Then we fix the inner radius to 1.5mm and observe the effect of different dielectric materials by calculating the thickness of the dielectric to have the phase velocity of the beam be approximately equal to the speed of light ($v_\phi = 0.998c$) at a working frequency of 165 GHz. The computed values are presented in Table 3.

Dielectric constant (ϵ_r)	Calculated dielectric thickness (μm)
2	193
3.75	125
8	94

Table 3: This table shows the dielectric thickness for different dielectric materials, where $a = 1.5mm$, and $v_\phi = 0.998c$.

Table 3 shows that by varying the dielectric material, we can alter the thickness of the dielectric medium inside the waveguide. In general, for a material with a higher dielectric constant, a lower dielectric layer would suffice.

4 Conclusions

This study was conducted to perform analytical calculations on the dielectric waveguide design of the TWAC (Tera-Hertz Wave Accelerating Cavity) project. With the THz-driven particle acceleration, we have the potential to develop compact, high-energy accelerators for a variety of usages in medicine and scientific research.

A partially filled circular waveguide is proposed as the accelerating structure to transmit variable fields as progressive waves using higher frequencies (considerably higher than the frequencies used in conventional RF structures), and in this study, we used a frequency of 165 GHz.

In this study, first, the problem of the circular waveguide was numerically solved for a given geometry (for fixed a and b), a selected dielectric material, and a given frequency. We observed four different roots for the basic equation, which corresponds to four different accelerating modes. The fifth root was also observed when we decreased the step size of the x-axis but we were only interested in the first four modes (i.e. first four roots).

Then the cutoff wavenumbers related to both mediums were plotted against one another and compared with the expected results from [1]. Here, the behavior of $k_{c_2}a$ followed the same pattern depicted in [1] against $k_{c_1}a$ (for purely real values of $k_{c_1}a$). This directly validated the algorithms we implemented. The same graph could be extended to take into account the purely imaginary $k_{c_1}a$ values as well, which could potentially be an interesting expansion, and an additional validation.

The cutoff frequencies for different accelerating modes were determined, and then it was followed by comparing the calculated normalized cutoff wavelength with that of [1]. The results were highly accurate for two decimal points which again validated our developed algorithms.

Selecting an appropriate value for the dielectric thickness of the waveguide is significant since the electric breakdown is the major limit of accelerating the field to a higher value, and the threshold breakdown and the dielectric constant are unique to a given dielectric material.

We investigated the dielectric thickness for different values of the inner radius to have the phase velocity of the beam be approximately equal to the speed of light ($v_\phi = 0.998c$) at a working frequency of 165 GHz. We observed that the thickness of the dielectric decreases when we increase the inner radius. When the calculated values were compared with the observed values using CST, they showed a strong similarity which directly confirmed the accuracy of our computation algorithm. Additionally, it was noted that for a material with a higher dielectric constant, a lower dielectric thickness would be enough.

5 Literature Cited

References

- [1] Christopher T. M. Chang and John W. Dawson. Propagation of electromagnetic waves in a partially dielectric filled circular waveguide. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 41(11):4493–4500, 1970.
- [2] D.M. Pozar. *Microwave Engineering, 4th Edition*. Wiley, 2011.
- [3] Abel Pires and Guillaume Martinet. Accélération de paquets d'électrons ultracourt par un champ thz guidé dans un diélectrique, 2021.
- [4] Vishal Kesari. Metal- and dielectric-loaded waveguide: An artificial material for tailoring the waveguide propagation characteristics. In Man-Gui Han, editor, *Electromagnetic Materials and Devices*, chapter 13. IntechOpen, Rijeka, 2019.
- [5] Maleesh Dissanayake Guillaume Martinet. Analytical-calculations-on-twac. <https://github.com/Maleesh98/Analytical-Calculations-on-TWAC>.
- [6] NumPy Development Team. Numpy v1.24 manual. <https://numpy.org/doc/stable/>, 2021.
- [7] Matplotlib Development Team. Matplotlib 3.3.3 documentation: Pyplot. https://matplotlib.org/stable/api/pyplot_summary.html, 2021.
- [8] SciPy Development Team. Scipy 1.7.0 reference guide: Special functions. <https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/special.html>, 2021.
- [9] SciPy Development Team. Scipy 1.7.0 reference guide: Optimization and fitting. <https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/optimize.html>, 2021.
- [10] Python Software Foundation. Python 3.10.0 documentation: The cmath module. <https://docs.python.org/3/library/cmath.html>, 2021.

6 Acknowledgement

I am really thankful to my supervisor Dr. Guillaume Martinet, for his immense support while taking his valuable time for useful and detailed discussions which hugely helped me to complete this project successfully. Additionally, I would like to thank Prof. Sophie Kazamias and Dr. Christelle Bruni for arranging this internship for me. Similarly, I gratefully express my gratitude to Laboratoire de Physique des 2 Infinis Irène Joliot-Curie for giving me this opportunity.

7 Python scripts used in this study

All the python scripts are available at [5].

Important:

The following Python packages were utilized in the study.

1. **NumPy:** NumPy is a library for Python that allows working with large arrays of numbers and performing mathematical operations on them. Mostly used in scientific computing and data analysis. More information at [6].
2. **Matplotlib.pyplot:** This is a module in the Matplotlib library in Python that provides a convenient interface for plotting data and creating visualizations. More information at [7].
3. **Scipy.special:** This is a module in the SciPy library in Python that provides a collection of mathematical functions including special mathematical functions, such as the Bessel functions, the Neumann functions, and the Legendre polynomials which makes the introduction of these functions to the computations more direct. More information at [8].
4. **Scipy.optimize:** This provides several optimization algorithms, such as scalar and multi-dimensional minimization algorithms, curve fitting, and root finding algorithms. In this study, this is mainly used to the task of root finding. More information at [9].
5. **Cmath:** This is a module in the Python standard library that provides support for complex number operations. This was utilized to take into account the complex wave numbers in the study. More information at [10].

7.1 Solving the general equation

Remarks:

Here, `lhs_function(x)` takes `x` as the input and provides the value of the left-hand side of Equation 44 for the selected `x` value. Also, `rhs_function(x)` takes `x` as the input and

provides the value of the left-hand side of Equation 44. Then we solve this equation using `func_diff(x)`, with appropriate initial guesses. Then the results are visualized in a plot. (This plot can also be used to determine the initial guesses to solve the main equation).

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import scipy.special as sp
import scipy.optimize as opt

# the initial conditions
Eps = 6.1
a = 0.03568
k0 = (20*(np.pi))/3 # le nombre d'onde de l'onde incidente

# defining the left hand side of the equation
def lhs_function(x):

    # fixing a and b
    a = 0.03568
    b = 0.05567
    # consider the first order of the Bessel function
    n = 1

    # y interms of x
    y = np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2)))

    # Rm original
    rmori = ((sp.yn(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.jn(n, y)))-((sp.jn(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.yn(n, y)))
    # Rm derivative
    rmdr = ((sp.yn(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.jvp(n, y)))-((sp.jn(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.yvp(n, y)))
    # Sm original
    smori = ((sp.yvp(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.jn(n, y)))-((sp.jvp(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.yn(n, y)))
    # Sm derivative
    smdr = ((sp.yvp(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.jvp(n, y)))-((sp.jvp(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.yvp(n, y)))

    # lhs value (using the equation)
    lhsarr = (((sp.jvp(n, x))/(x*sp.jn(n, x)))-((Eps*rmdr)/(y*rmori)))*
    (((sp.jvp(n, x))/(x*sp.jn(n, x)))-((smdr)/(y*smori)))

    return lhsarr

# defining the right hand side of the equation
def rhs_function(x):
    return ((1/(x**2))-Eps/((np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2))))**2))*((1/(x**2))
    -1/((np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2))))**2))
```

```

# Generate data points for the x-axis: this is the selected x range
x = np.linspace(0, 6, 100)

# Calculate the right hand side function values
value_rhs = rhs_function(x)

# Calculate the left hand side function values
value_lhs = lhs_function(x)

# solving the equation

initial_guess = np.array([0.8, 2.5, 3.1, 4]) # initial guesses (looking at the graph)

# Define the difference between the two functions as a function of x
def func_diff(x):
    return lhs_function(x)- rhs_function(x)

# Use the root function to find the root of the difference
root = opt.root(func_diff, initial_guess)

x_root_value = root.x

# Print the root
print('The intersecting points of the plots: ',root.x)

# finding the f(x) values related to roots
y_value_for_x_root_value = rhs_function(x_root_value)
print('f(x) values related to roots: ',y_value_for_x_root_value)

colors = ['red', 'green', 'blue', 'orange', 'purple']

# draw the plot

# Create a figure and axis
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 8), dpi=300)

# Adjust x-axis labels font size
for tick in ax.get_xticklabels():
    tick.set_fontsize(12)

# Adjust y-axis labels font size
for tick in ax.get_yticklabels():
    tick.set_fontsize(12)

```

```
# Plot the first function
ax.plot(x, value_rhs, label='Right hand side')

# Plot the second function
ax.plot(x, value_lhs, label='Left hand side')

# plot the roots
for i in range(len(x_root_value)):
    ax.plot(x_root_value[i], y_value_for_x_root_value[i], 'o', color=colors[i], label='Root')

# Add labels and a title
ax.set_xlabel('x', fontsize=15)
ax.set_ylabel('f(x)', fontsize=15)
#ax.set_title('General Equation')

# Add a legend
ax.legend()

# Limit the y-axis values
ax.set_ylim(-2, 6)

# Add a grid to the plot
ax.grid(True, linestyle='-.', color='grey')

# Show the plot
plt.show()
```

7.2 Diagram of $k_{c_2}a$ as a function of $k_{c_1}a$ for the first 4 modes for 1 GHz

Remarks:

Here, `y_value(x)` generates the `y` value for a given `x` value, because in order to draw the plot, we need the `y` value for the obtained roots (`x`). We use the previously obtained results as the roots here (for the 1 GHz case).

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import scipy.special as sp
import scipy.optimize as opt

# intial conditions
Eps = 6.1
a = 0.03568
k0 = (20*(np.pi))/3 # le nombre d'onde de l'onde incidente for a 1GHz wave

# Define the function to generate y values for a given x value
def y_value(x):
    y = np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2)))
    return y

# Generate data points for the x-axis
x = np.linspace(0, 4, 100)

# Calculate y-values for the selected x values
y_value_for_x = y_value(x)

# the intersecting points of the two sides of the general equation
x_root = np.array([0.90593754, 2.5176104, 3.22187473, 4.00958222])
# this was obtained for 1 GHz wave previously

# y value related to x value using the function
y_value_for_x_root = y_value(x_root)

colors = ['blue', 'red', 'green', 'orange', 'purple']

# Create a figure and axis
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(5, 3), dpi=300)

# Plot the function, x and y values: blue curve
ax.plot(x, y_value_for_x)

# Plot the roots on the curve
```

```
for i in range(len(x_root)):
    ax.plot(x_root[i], y_value_for_x_root[i], 'o', color=colors[i], label='')

# Add labels and a title
ax.set_xlabel('kc1a (x)')
ax.set_ylabel('kc2a (y)')
ax.set_title('The kc1a vs kc2a diagram for the first 4 modes for 1 GHz')

# Limit the y-axis values
ax.set_ylim(0, 6)

# Add a grid to the plot
ax.grid(True, linestyle='-.', color='grey')

# Show the plot
plt.show()
```

7.3 Diagram of $k_{c_2}a$ as a function of $k_{c_1}a$ for different frequencies

Remarks:

Here, `roots_different_freq(p, q, m, ini1, ini2, ini3, ini4)` function takes seven different inputs (the starting frequency, the ending frequency, `m` is the number of intervals to slice the frequency domain and the initial conditions related to the four modes respectively), and outputs the roots of the general equation for a given frequency.

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import scipy.special as sp
import scipy.optimize as opt

# intial conditions
Eps = 6.1
a = 0.03568

def roots_different_freq(p, q, m, ini1, ini2, ini3, ini4):

    #m is the number of intervals to slice the frequency domain

    # Generate different frequencies
    ff = np.linspace(p, q, m) # generating m equally spaced frequencies from p to q GHz

    # related k0 values
    k_array = (20*(np.pi)*ff)/3

    print('The roots of the equations for given frequency range: ')

    for i in range(m):
        k0 = k_array[i]
        # Generate data points for the x-axis
        xarr = np.linspace(0, 10, 100)

        # Define the function to be plotted (right hand side)
        def rhs_function(x):
            rhsarr = ((1/(x**2))- (Eps/((np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2))))**2)))*
            ((1/(x**2))- (1/((np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2))))**2)))
            return rhsarr

        # Define the function to be plotted (kc1 and kc2 values/ x and y)
        def y_value(x):
            y = np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2)))
            return y
```

```

# (left hand side)

def lhs_function(x):

    a = 0.03568
    b = 0.05567
    n = 1

    y = np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2)))

    rmori = ((sp.yn(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.jn(n, y)))
    -((sp.jn(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.yn(n, y)))
    rmder = ((sp.yn(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.jvp(n, y)))
    -((sp.jn(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.yvp(n, y)))
    smori = ((sp.yvp(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.jn(n, y)))
    -((sp.jvp(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.yn(n, y)))
    smder = ((sp.yvp(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.jvp(n, y)))
    -((sp.jvp(n, ((b/a)*y)))*(sp.yvp(n, y)))

    lhsarr = (((sp.jvp(n, x))/(x*sp.jn(n, x)))-((Eps*rmder)/(y*rmori)))*
    (((sp.jvp(n, x))/(x*sp.jn(n, x)))-((smder)/(y*smori)))

    return lhsarr

yrhs = rhs_function(xarr)
ylhs = lhs_function(xarr)

#x0 = np.array([0.9, 2.7, 3.4, 4]) # initial guesses (looking at the graph)
x0 = np.array([ini1, ini2, ini3, ini4]) # initial guesses (looking at the graph)

# Define the difference between the two functions as a function of x
def func_diff(x):
    return lhs_function(x)- rhs_function(x)

# Use the root function to find the root of the difference
root = opt.root(func_diff, x0)

rootxval = root.x

# Print the root

print(root.x)

roots_different_freq(0, 1, 20, 0.9, 2.7, 3.4, 4)

```

Remarks:

Then we execute the defined function with selected initial conditions as shown above and get the roots for different frequencies from 0 to 1 GHz. The selection of the frequency domain is arbitrary. We can expand the range to obtain more roots.

Then we manually select the appropriate set of k values, and the set of roots, looking at the generated results for roots. Here the Python script is provided only for the upper part (above the black line) of the diagram. To consider the lower part, we simply have to change the equation to calculate the y value. The rest of the algorithm follows the same, but it is important to use the appropriate initial conditions for each time.

```
# the complete set of k values with proper set of intersections
# this set of k values were manually chosen looking at the roots by
running the previous code

selected_k_upper = np.array([ 0.0, 1.10231321, 2.20462642, 3.30693964, 4.40925285,
    5.51156606, 6.61387927, 7.71619248, 8.81850569, 9.92081891,
    11.02313212, 12.12544533, 13.22775854, 14.33007175, 15.43238497,
    16.53469818, 17.63701139, 18.7393246 , 19.84163781, 20.94395102,
    22.04626424, 23.14857745, 24.25089066, 25.35320387,
    26.45551708, 27.55783029])

# let's generate the y values (kc2a) to draw the plots related to these selected k values

m = len(selected_k_upper)

# this is our y curves
y_curve_for_selected_k_upper = [0 for _ in range(m)]

for i in range(m):
    k0 = selected_k_upper[i]
    # Generate data points for the x-axis
    x_array = np.linspace(0, 4, 100)

    # Define the function to be plotted (kc1 and kc2 values/ x and y)
    def y_value(x):
        y = np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2)))
        return y

    y_curve_for_selected_k_upper[i] = y_value(x_array)

# let's manually write the roots (intersecting points) to draw the plots
# this is obtained using the previous results

selected_roots_upper = np.array([[1.18005097, 2.92271031, 3.41702673, 4.06870381],
    [1.17951698, 2.92167539, 3.41651715, 4.0685089 ],
    [1.17790988, 2.9185675, 3.41498731, 4.06792542],
```

```

[1.17521416, 2.91337725, 3.41243401, 4.06695717],
[1.17140349, 2.90608907, 3.40885188, 4.06561039],
[1.16644007, 2.89668128, 3.40423343, 4.06389365],
[1.16027353, 2.88512622, 3.39856904, 4.06181774],
[1.15283956, 2.87139041, 3.39184704, 4.05939543],
[1.14405797, 2.85543479, 3.38405367, 4.05664129],
[1.13383022, 2.83721488, 3.37517319, 4.05357144],
[1.12203618, 2.81668115, 3.3651879, 4.05020325],
[1.10852987, 2.79377928, 3.35407827, 4.04655508],
[1.09313397, 2.76845057, 3.34182297, 4.04264596],
[1.07563242, 2.7406324, 3.32839906, 4.03849532],
[1.05576064, 2.71025874, 3.31378213, 4.03412264],
[1.03319207, 2.6772609, 3.29794652, 4.02954722],
[1.00751952, 2.64156824, 3.28086551, 4.02478788],
[0.9782284, 2.6031093, 3.2625117, 4.01986269],
[0.94465733, 2.56181302, 3.24285733, 4.0147888 ],
[0.90593754, 2.5176104, 3.22187473, 4.00958222],
[0.86089485, 2.47043645, 3.19953685, 4.00425765],
[0.80788054, 2.42023269, 3.17581797, 3.99882837],
[0.74445236, 2.36694973, 3.15069443, 3.99330618],
[0.66669512, 2.3105506, 3.12414558, 3.98770126],
[0.56748292, 2.25101347, 3.09615486, 3.98202223],
[0.43038382, 2.18833359, 3.06671146, 3.97627606]])

```

```

colors = ['blue', 'red', 'green', 'orange', 'purple']

```

```

# finding the y values for the selected x roots (above)
m = len(selected_k_upper)

```

```

# this is the y value related to x
y_value_for_selected_roots_upper = [0 for _ in range(m)]

```

```

for i in range(m):
    k0 = selected_k_upper[i]

```

```

    # Define the function to be plotted (kc1 and kc2 values/ x and y)
    def y_value(x):
        y = np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2)))
        return y

```

```

    y_value_for_selected_roots_upper[i] = y_value(selected_roots_upper[i])

```

```

# we want to mark the rest of the k values related to different frequencies
from 0 GHz to 18.6 GHz.

```

```

# In the graph it is related to marking the upper section

Eps = 6.1
a = 0.03568

# Generate different frequencies
m = 400
ff = np.linspace(0, 18.6, m) # different frequencies from 0 GHz to 18.6 GHz.

all_k_upper = (20*(np.pi)*ff)/3

# generating related curves
y_curve_for_all_k_upper = [0 for _ in range(m)]

for i in range(m):
    k0 = all_k_upper[i]
    # Generate data points for the x-axis
    x_array = np.linspace(0, 4, 100)

    # Define the function to be plotted (kc1 and kc2 values/ x and y)
    def y_value(x):
        y = np.sqrt((x**2)+((Eps-1)*(k0**2)*(a**2)))
        return y

    y_curve_for_all_k_upper[i] = y_value(x_array)

# drawing results

# Create a figure and axis
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 8), dpi=300)

x_array = np.linspace(0, 4, 100)

# Plot the second function
for i in range(len(y_curve_for_all_k_upper)):
    ax.plot(x_array, y_curve_for_all_k_upper[i])

for i in range(len(y_curve_for_selected_k_upper)):
    # Plot the function
    ax.plot(x_array, y_curve_for_selected_k_upper[i])

    x_value_selected_root = selected_roots_upper[i]
    y_value_selected_root = y_value_for_selected_roots_upper[i]

    # Plot the second function

```

```
    for i in range(len(x_value_selected_root)):
        ax.plot(x_value_selected_root[i], y_value_selected_root[i], 'o',
                color=colors[i], label='')

# Add labels and a title
ax.set_xlabel('kc1a (x)')
ax.set_ylabel('kc2a (y)')
ax.set_title('The kc1a vs kc2a diagram for the first 4 modes')

# Limit the y-axis values
ax.set_ylim(0, 6)

# Add a grid to the plot
ax.grid(True, linestyle='-.', color='grey')

# Show the plot
plt.show()
```

7.4 Cutoff frequency

Remarks: Here, the main function `normalized_cutoff_freq(n, ratio_b_a, Eps, p, q, r, s)` takes 7 different inputs (the order of the Bessel function related to the mode m , the ratio between radii, dielectric constant, and initial conditions to find intersecting points in order), and outputs the normalized cutoff frequencies ($\lambda/2b$) according to Chang's theory [1].

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import scipy.special as sp
import scipy.optimize as opt

def normalized_cutoff_freq(n, ratio_b_a, Eps, p, q, r, s):

    # DEFINING THE THREE MAIN FUNCTIONS

    # Define the function to be plotted: TO FIND THE Y VALUES
    def cutoff_y_value(x):
        y = np.sqrt(Eps)*x # now, this is the modified y when the propagation
                           constant is zero.
        return y

    # Define the function to be plotted (right hand side)
    def cutoff_rhs_function(x):

        y = np.sqrt(Eps)*x

        rhsarr = ((1/(x**2))-(Eps/(y**2)))*((1/(x**2))-(1/(y**2)))

        return rhsarr

    def cutoff_lhs_function(x):

        y = np.sqrt(Eps)*x

        rmori = ((sp.yn(n, ((ratio_b_a)*y)))*(sp.jn(n, y)))
                -((sp.jn(n, ((ratio_b_a)*y)))*(sp.yn(n, y)))
        rmder = ((sp.yn(n, ((ratio_b_a)*y)))*(sp.jvp(n, y)))
                -((sp.jn(n, ((ratio_b_a)*y)))*(sp.yvp(n, y)))
        smori = ((sp.yvp(n, ((ratio_b_a)*y)))*(sp.jn(n, y)))
                -((sp.jvp(n, ((ratio_b_a)*y)))*(sp.yn(n, y)))
        smder = ((sp.yvp(n, ((ratio_b_a)*y)))*(sp.jvp(n, y)))
                -((sp.jvp(n, ((ratio_b_a)*y)))*(sp.yvp(n, y)))

        lhsarr = (((sp.jvp(n, x))/(x*sp.jn(n, x)))-((Eps*rmder)/(y*rmori)))
```

```

    *(((sp.jvp(n, x))/(x*sp.jn(n, x)))-((smdr)/(y*smori)))

    return lhsarr

# THE GRAPHS TO BE PLOTTED

x_array = np.linspace(0, 6, 100)
y_value_rhs = cutoff_rhs_function(x_array)
y_value_lhs = cutoff_lhs_function(x_array)

# Create a figure and axis
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 8), dpi=300)

# Plot the first function
ax.plot(x_array, y_value_rhs, label='Right hand side')

# Plot the second function
ax.plot(x_array, y_value_lhs, label='Left hand side')

# Add labels and a title
ax.set_xlabel('x')
ax.set_ylabel('y')
ax.set_title('General Equation')

# Add a legend
ax.legend()

# Limit the y-axis values
ax.set_ylim(-2, 6)

# Add a grid to the plot
ax.grid(True, linestyle='-.', color='grey')

# Show the plot
plt.show()

#

# TO FIND THE ROOTS

x0 = np.array([p, q, r, s]) # initial guesses (looking at the graph)

# Define the difference between the two functions as a function of x
def func_diff(x):
    #return cutoff_lhs_function(x)- cutoff_rhs_function(x)

```

```

    return cutoff_lhs_function(x) # since the rhs accounts for zero values,
    we can simply neglect that.

# Use the root function to find the root of the difference
root = opt.root(func_diff, x0)

x_root = root.x

# TO FIND THE NORMALIZED WAVELENGTHS

normwavelen = (np.pi/x_root)*(1/ratio_b_a) # this is using the equation

# RESULTS

print('FINAL RESULTS: -----')
print('The order of Bessel Function: ', n)
print('Ratio b/a: ',ratio_b_a)
print('Dielectric Constant: ',Eps)
print('X values(roots): ',root.x)
print('Normalized wavelengths (lambda/2b): ', normwavelen)

```

7.5 Dielectric thickness

Remarks:

Here the main function `dielectric_thickness(n, Eps, a, f, phase_velocity_ratio, p)` takes 6 different inputs (the order of the Bessel function related to the mode m , the dielectric constant, the inner radius (a), the working frequency (f), the phase velocity, and initial condition to find intersecting points respectively), and outputs the dielectric thickness.

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import scipy.special as sp
import scipy.optimize as opt

import cmath

def dielectric_thickness(n, Eps, a, f, phase_velocity_ratio, p):

    f0 = f*(10**9) # the working frequency
    c = 3*(10**8)
    vphi = phase_velocity_ratio*c # the required phase velocity

    # calculating wave numbers:

    k0 = (2*(np.pi)*f0)/(c) # le nombre d'onde de l'onde incidente
    kz = (2*(np.pi)*f0)/(vphi) # propagation constant
    k1 = cmath.sqrt((k0**2)-(kz**2)) # wave number in vacuum
    k2 = cmath.sqrt((Eps*(k0**2))-(kz**2)) # wave number in dielectric

    print('k0: ', k0)
    print('kz: ', kz)
    print('k1: ', k1)
    print('k2: ', k2)

    # calculating x and y values: (related to the selected values)

    x_value = k1*a
    y_value = k2*a

    print('x: ', x_value)
    print('y: ', y_value)

    # right hand side of the equation

    value_rhs = ((1/(x_value**2))-(Eps/(y_value**2)))*((1/(x_value**2))-(1/(y_value**2)))
```

```

print('right hand side value: ', value_rhs)

pos = x_value # pos represents the x value
yval = y_value.real # considering the real part of the solution

# defining the main function:

def lhs_function_in_b(x): # here x represents b, without the loss of generality
    # needed to make it a function of x to find the roots later

    rmori = ((sp.yn(n, ((x/a)*yval)))*(sp.jn(n, yval)))
    -((sp.jn(n, ((x/a)*yval)))*(sp.yn(n, yval)))
    rmder = ((sp.yn(n, ((x/a)*yval)))*(sp.jvp(n, yval)))
    -((sp.jn(n, ((x/a)*yval)))*(sp.yvp(n, yval)))
    smori = ((sp.yvp(n, ((x/a)*yval)))*(sp.jn(n, yval)))
    -((sp.jvp(n, ((x/a)*yval)))*(sp.yn(n, yval)))
    smder = ((sp.yvp(n, ((x/a)*yval)))*(sp.jvp(n, yval)))
    -((sp.jvp(n, ((x/a)*yval)))*(sp.yvp(n, yval)))

    lhs = (((sp.jvp(n, pos))/(pos*sp.jn(n, pos)))-((Eps*rmder)/(yval*rmori)))
    *(((sp.jvp(n, pos))/(pos*sp.jn(n, pos)))-((smder)/(yval*smori)))-value_rhs

    return lhs

# THE GRAPHS TO BE PLOTTED

b_array = np.linspace(a, a+0.0005, 100)

lhs_values_for_b = lhs_function_in_b(b_array)

# Create a figure and axis
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 8), dpi=300)

# Plot the first function
ax.plot(b_array, lhs_values_for_b, label='F(b)')

# Add labels and a title
ax.set_xlabel('b')
ax.set_ylabel('F(b)')
#ax.set_title('General Equation')

# Add a legend
ax.legend()

# Add a grid to the plot

```

```

ax.grid(True, linestyle='-.', color='grey')

# Show the plot
plt.show()

# FINDING THE ROOT OF THE EQUATION

x0 = np.array([p]) # initial guesses (looking at the graph)

# Define the difference between the two functions as a function of x
def func_diff(x):
    return lhs_function_in_b(x).real # since the rhs accounts for zero values,
    we can simply neglect that.

# Use the root function to find the root of the difference
root = opt.root(func_diff, x0)

b_root = root.x

# Print the root
print('The value of x (intersection point): ',root.x)

print('Dielectric thickness for a = x_value m: (in microns)',(b_root-a)*10**6)
# in micrometers

```